

ECONOMETRICS

**A Credit Default Swap based model to measure
the Financial Stability of financial institutions in
the U.S. during COVID-19**

Author:

M.M.F. WOELDERS S3417565

Supervisor:

dr. K.W. CHAU

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Supervisor:

DR. K.W. CHAU

Second assessor:

DR. A.A. TSVETKOV

A CREDIT DEFAULT SWAP BASED MODEL TO MEASURE THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE U.S. DURING COVID-19**Abstract**

This paper investigates how the financial stability of a firm can be modelled using Credit Default Swaps and how this model can be applied to measure the financial stability of financial institutions in the U.S. during COVID-19. An algorithm based on the theoretical framework around Credit Default Swaps and financial stability of Merton (1974), Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) and Suh, Jang, and Ahn (2013) will be developed. Numerical experiments show that the developed algorithm converges in the setting of this paper. Using CDS data, the model will be used to measure the the financial stability of nine major banks in the U.S. during COVID-19. The results show that all nine banks have been relatively financially stable throughout the entire sample period. In addition, the results show that the negative effect of COVID-19 on the financial stability of each individual bank dies out over time. Based on some odd MLE parameter values obtained from the model, the reliability of the model used in this paper should be questioned.

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1 Introduction

To maintain financial stability, financial regulators use various policy tools not only to prevent individual financial institutions from defaulting but also to control the riskiness of the financial system as a whole (i.e., systemic risk) (Suh et al., 2013). Data on Credit Default Swaps (CDS) may be used for measuring systemic risk (Suh et al., 2013), as well as for measuring the financial stability of an individual financial institution. Credit Default Swaps, introduced in 1997 by JP Morgan, have become the most common form of credit derivative (Cont et al., 2010). Since Credit Default Swaps played an important role during the financial crisis, many studies have been conducted with respect to this. Some relevant papers include (Stulz, 2010), (Senarath and Copp, 2015) and (Terzi and Ulucay, 2011).

Credit Default Swaps are essentially whole life insurances on the "life" of an institution. It is a contract between the protection buyer and protection seller. The protection buyer insures itself against the default of an asset. The protection seller pays a fixed premium to the protection buyer until the maturity date or until there is a default, whichever occurs first. To come to such an agreement, the Credit Default Swap needs to be priced in a fair way such that both parties will accept the contract. One can imagine that the price of the credit default swap is highly dependent on the probability of default of the asset insured. In fact, the valuation of a credit default swap requires estimates of the risk-neutral probability that the asset insured will default at different future times (Hull and White, 2000). A higher probability of default will result in a higher CDS price and vice versa. Furthermore, the maturity date of the CDS is closely related to the CDS price. The longer the duration of the contract, the higher the probability of default within this time, which leads to higher CDS prices.

Due to the significant impact placed on the economy and society by COVID-19, measuring the riskiness of the financial system as a whole seems to be more important than ever before. The Great Recession, which started with the fall of Lehman Brothers in September 2008, has painfully shown the importance of measuring systemic risk. Financial regulators could prevent another financial crisis like the one in 2008 by making policies based on the systemic risk. Additionally, individual institutions could adjust their business strategy based on their financial stability and the financial stability of their competitors. A great deal of research on systemic risk is done. For example, Lehar (2005) used a risk management approach to measure the systemic risk. He proposed a new method to measure and monitor the risk in a banking system. Cont and Minca (2016) presented a network model for investigating the impact on systemic risk of central clearing of over the counter (OTC) Credit Default Swaps. Other interesting examples of relevant literature about systemic risk include (Nijsskens and Wagner, 2011), (Puliga, Caldarelli, and Battiston, 2014) and (Markose, Giannante, and Shaghghi, 2012).

The literature on pricing theory is extensive. Black and Scholes (1973) developed a complete general equilibrium theory for option pricing. Merton (1974) clarified and extended this model. He developed a model for pricing corporate liabilities, which can also be used for the pricing of almost all other financial instruments. In the approach of Merton (1974) to price corporate debt, interest rates are assumed to be constant, and the default risk of a bond is modeled using option pricing theory. One of the drawbacks of this approach is that default is assumed to occur only when the firm exhausts its assets (Longstaff and Schwartz, 1995). Firms usually default long before the firm's assets are exhausted (Longstaff and Schwartz, 1995). Black and Cox (1976) made a more realistic assumption by defining the default of a firm when the value of the firm's asset reaches a lower threshold. Despite this advantage, they also assume a constant interest rate, just as the traditional Black-Scholes-Merton framework for valuing risky debt. Longstaff and Schwartz (1995) extended the model of Black and Cox (1976) and incorporated the interest rate risk as well. Since firms adjust outstanding debt levels in response to changes in firm value, Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) proposed a structural model of default with stochastic interest rates that captures the mean reverting behaviour of log leverage ratios. They developed this model based on the existing Black-Scholes-Merton framework. Compared to traditional structural models of default, the credit spreads generated from their model seem to be more consistent with empirical findings.

Moreover, Suh et al. (2013) adopted the model proposed by Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) for individual financial institutions. They provided a method to measure systemic risk based on CDS data and applied this method to measure the systemic risk around The Great Recession. They employed their method to measure systemic risk for a group of 22 large financial institutions in the U.S. for the period from March 2006 to August 2010. Since CDS premiums are difficult to obtain, they have not been used a lot in measuring systemic risks. However, CDS premiums have desirable properties for measuring systemic risk, since they are directly related to default probabilities. Consequently, Huang, Zhou, and Zhu (2009) inferred default probabilities from CDS premiums and then combined them with equity return correlations to simulate credit events.

The goal of this study is to show how the financial stability of a firm can be modelled using Credit Default Swaps and how one could apply this model to measure the financial stability of financial institution in the U.S. during COVID-19. The research question that will be answered in this paper is: "What do Credit Default Swap premiums reveal about the financial stability of financial institutions in the U.S. during COVID-19?".

This paper builds on the framework developed by Suh et al. (2013). Since their paper lacks the actual implementation of their model, their paper is not re-

producibile and barely useful for further research. However, their approach towards the determination of an institutions financial stability is an interesting one that should be investigated further. This paper will try to bridge the gap between the existing theoretical CDS based model of Suh et al. (2013) to measure financial stability and its implementations. Besides that, the financial stability of major financial institutions in the U.S. will be investigated during COVID-19. The hypotheses is that the U.S. financial institutions have become significantly less financially stable after the introduction of COVID-19.

In the next section, the methodology used in this paper will be explained. In section 3 a description of the data will be given. Then the implementation of the model is explained in section 4. In section 5, the model will be applied to measure the financial stability of nine major banks in the U.S. during COVID-19. In section 6, a conclusion will be given. Finally, some further research suggestions will be given in section 7. An overview of the parameters used in this paper can be found in Appendix A.

2 Methodology

Consider a continuous time economy with N financial institutions $j = (1, \dots, N)$. This paper assumes that there is a default when the asset of a financial institution falls below a certain threshold. Or in other words, when the value of the threshold $K_{j,t}$ of institution j is higher than the asset $V_{j,t}$ of institution j at a moment of time, a default occurs. Let us define the leverage ratio as $L_{j,t} = K_{j,t}/V_{j,t}$ for institution j at time t . Then a default occurs when the log leverage ratio $l_{j,t} = \ln(K_{j,t}/V_{j,t}) = \ln(K_{j,t}) - \ln(V_{j,t})$ is positive. Given data on CDS premiums over time, the probability of default over time for each financial institution j can be obtained. Together with assumed parameters the log leverage ratio $l_{j,t}$ for each financial institution over time can be obtained. With this data, we can construct a log-likelihood function and estimate the real parameters of interest $\Theta_j = (\mu_j, \sigma_j, \lambda_j, \nu_j)$ by applying the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method (Fisher, 1925). With these parameter estimates $\hat{\Theta}_j = (\hat{\mu}_j, \hat{\sigma}_j, \hat{\lambda}_j, \hat{\nu}_j)$, the corresponding log leverage ratio data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$ can be constructed. The MLE method can be applied again. This process repeats itself, until the parameter estimates converge.

2.1 Log leverage dynamics

Recall that the log leverage ratio is defined as $l_{j,t} = \ln(K_{j,t}/V_{j,t}) = \ln(K_{j,t}) - \ln(V_{j,t})$. Note that the log leverage ratio for institution j depends on two different variables which change over time; the asset value $V_{j,t}$ and the default threshold $K_{j,t}$. It is widely accepted that the asset dynamics of institution j is covered by the geometric Brownian motion (Akansu and Torun, 2015), that is:

$$\frac{dV_{j,t}}{V_{j,t}} = \mu_j dt + \sigma_j dW_{j,t}, \quad (1)$$

where $W_{j,t} = \epsilon\sqrt{t}$; $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1)$ denotes the standard Wiener process, μ_j denotes the expected drift and σ_j the volatility. Although it is widely accepted that the geometric Brownian motion is used, it is not certain whether this is the correct nor the best way to model the asset dynamics. Then we also have:

$$d\ln(V_{j,t}) = (\mu_j - 0.5\sigma_j^2)dt + \sigma_j dW_{j,t} \quad (2)$$

In the widely used credit risk model of Merton (1974) and in the models of Black and Cox (1976) and Longstaff and Schwartz (1995), the default threshold $K_{j,t}$ does not change over time. Since more debt tends to be issued when the log leverage ratio is less than some target value and vice versa, this paper follows Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) approach where the default threshold $K_{j,t}$ does change over time. They specify the dynamics of $K_{j,t}$ as follows:

$$d\ln(K_{j,t}) = \lambda_j(\ln(V_{j,t}) - \nu_j - \ln(K_{j,t}))dt, \quad (3)$$

where λ_j denotes the institution's speed of adjustment to its log leverage ratio target and v_j denotes the institution's log leverage ratio target. Please note that the log leverage ratio target v_j is in fact the opposite of the actual log leverage ratio target. So a positive log leverage ratio target v_j , corresponds to the aim towards a negative log leverage ratio.

Since the dynamics of both $V_{j,t}$ and $K_{j,t}$ are specified, the dynamics of $l_{j,t}$ follows from Itô's lemma:

$$\begin{aligned} dl_{j,t} &= \lambda_j(\ln(V_{j,t}) - v_j - \ln(K_{j,t}))dt - (\mu_j - 0.5\sigma_j^2)dt - \sigma_j dW_{j,t} \\ &= (\lambda_j(-l_{j,t} - v_j) - (\mu_j - 0.5\sigma_j^2))dt - \sigma_j dW_{j,t} \\ &= \lambda_j(\bar{l} - l_{j,t})dt - \sigma_j dW_{j,t}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{l} = \frac{-\mu_j + 0.5\sigma_j^2}{\lambda_j} - v_j$.

Following Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001), $\sigma_j = 0.2$, $\lambda_j = 0.18$ and $\bar{l} = -1$ and $\mu_j = 0.001$ is taken as the base case. As a result, $v_j = 1.105$. Choosing $\lambda_j = 0.18$ falls close to the estimate of Fama and French (2000) ($\lambda_j \approx 0.1$).

2.2 Implied risk-neutral default probability from CDS premiums

A Credit Default Swap is an agreement between two parties; the protection buyer, and the protection seller. The protection buyer insures itself against the default of a specific asset. In exchange for this, the protection buyer pays a fixed annual premium to the protection seller until the maturity date or until there is a default, whichever occurs first. If a default occurs, the protection seller compensates the protection buyer for the loss given default (LGD).

By the principle of actuarial fairness, and following the framework of Duffie (1999) the expected present value of the CDS premium payments needs to be equal to the expected value of the protection payment, that is,

$$s_{j,t} \int_t^{t+T} e^{-rt} (1 - \int_0^\tau \psi_{j,u} du) d\tau = LGD_{j,t} \int_t^{t+T} e^{-rt} \psi_{j,\tau} d\tau, \quad (5)$$

where $\psi_{j,\tau}$ denotes the unconditional risk-neutral default density of the institution j , and $s_{j,t}$ denotes the CDS premium payment for the institution j . Under the assumption that $\psi_{j,\tau}$ does not change between t and $t+1$, we have:

$P(\text{Default between } t \text{ and } t+1) = \int_t^{t+1} \psi_{j,\tau} d\tau = \psi_{j,\tau}(t+1-t) = \psi_{j,\tau}$. As a result, the 1 year risk-neutral default probability is given by:

$$\psi_{j,\tau} = \frac{s_{j,t} \int_t^{t+1} e^{-rt} d\tau}{LGD_{j,t} \int_t^{t+1} e^{-rt} d\tau + s_{j,t} \int_t^{t+1} \tau e^{-rt} d\tau} \quad (6)$$

For simplicity $LGD_{j,t} = 1$ for all j and t . And so, $s_{j,t}$ is just the CDS premium value for institution j at time t .

2.3 Risk-neutral default probability and the log leverage ratios

Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) created a model that calculates the risk neutral default probability $Q(l_t, t)$ that a default occurs before time T , given the log leverage ratio l_t at time t . This model is based on the log leverage dynamics specified in section 2.1. The model is defined as follows:

$$Q(l_t, T) = \sum_{i=1}^n q_i \quad (7)$$

$$q_1 = \frac{\Phi(a_1)}{\Phi(b_{1/2})} \quad (8)$$

$$q_i = \frac{1}{\Phi(b_{1/2})} * (\Phi(a_i) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} q_j * \Phi(b_{i-j+1/2})), i = 2, \dots, n \quad (9)$$

$$a_i = \frac{M(i\Delta)}{S(i\Delta)} \quad (10)$$

$$b_i = \frac{L(i\Delta)}{S(i\Delta)} \quad (11)$$

$$M(\tau) = l_t e^{-\lambda\tau} + \bar{l}(1 - e^{-\lambda\tau}) \quad (12)$$

$$L(\tau) = \bar{l}(1 - e^{-\lambda\tau}) \quad (13)$$

$$S(\tau)^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{2\lambda}(1 - e^{-2\lambda\tau}) \quad (14)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the standard normal cumulative distribution function and $\Delta = \frac{T-t}{n}$

For $T = 1$, $Q(l_t, 1)$ is equal to the 1 year risk-neutral default probability implied from the CDS premiums. Together with the assumed parameters $\Theta_j = (\mu_j, \sigma_j, \lambda_j, \nu_j)$, the log leverage ratios $l_{j,t}$ can be obtained from (7)-(14). This results in the log leverage ratio data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$ corresponding to our assumed initial parameters. In this paper, $n=10$ is taken as the number of intervals.

2.4 Parameter estimation

From the log leverage ratio data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$ corresponding to the assumed initial parameters the maximum likelihood method can be used to obtain the actual MLE estimated parameters. To perform the MLE method to the obtained log leverage ratio data we need to construct the log likelihood function. Suh et al. (2013) derived this log likelihood function under the assumption that the data observations are discretely sampled with a fixed time interval Δ . That is,

$$l_{t+\Delta|t} \sim \mathcal{N}(l_t e^{-\lambda\Delta} + \bar{l}(1 - e^{-\lambda\Delta}), \frac{\sigma^2}{2\lambda} e^{-\lambda\Delta}(e^{2\lambda\Delta} - 1)) \quad (15)$$

And so, the corresponding log likelihood function is then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(L) = & -\frac{m-1}{2} \ln(2\pi) - \frac{m-1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{\sigma^2}{2\lambda} e^{-\lambda\Delta} (e^{2\lambda\Delta} - 1)\right) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=2}^m \frac{(l_i - l_{i-1} e^{-\lambda\Delta} - \bar{l}(1 - e^{-\lambda\Delta}))^2}{\frac{\sigma^2}{2\lambda} e^{-\lambda\Delta} (e^{2\lambda\Delta} - 1)} - \sum_{i=2}^m \ln\left(\frac{\partial Q(l_i, T)}{\partial l_i}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Here,

$$\frac{\partial Q(l, T)}{\partial l_i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial l}, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial q_1}{\partial l} = \frac{\varphi(a_i)}{\Phi(b_{1/2})} \frac{e^{-\lambda\Delta}}{S(\Delta)}, \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial l} = \frac{1}{\Phi(b_{1/2})} \left(\varphi(a_i) \frac{e^{-\lambda\Delta}}{S(i\Delta)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{\partial q_j}{\partial l} \Phi(b_{i-j+1/2}) \right) \quad (19)$$

where $\varphi(\cdot)$ denotes the standard normal distribution. By applying the maximum likelihood estimation method the final estimates of the parameters $\Theta_j = (\mu_j, \sigma_j, \lambda_j, \nu_j)$ can be obtained. Note that this log likelihood function is very complex. Besides that, the MLE method results in a four dimensional optimization problem. Therefore, Numerical Methods are needed to get to the final parameter estimates.

3 Data Description

Since banks have been the most important financial intermediaries in the economy, by providing liquidity transformation and monitoring services (Huang et al., 2009), nine major banks from the U.S. are considered for the application of the model. For each of these banks, data of their CDS premiums are obtained over time on a daily basis starting from 2015-10-29 to 2020-10-27. Figure 1 shows the CDS premiums over time for each individual bank from 2018-12-14 to 2020-10-27. This is the sample data that is used throughout the rest of the paper. The CDS premium prices are obtained from the Thomson Reuters Eikon

Figure 1: CDS premium in basispoints over time

database. They seem to follow the same pattern for each individual bank. The CDS prices are extremely stable from 2018-12-14 to 2020-03-02; the prices are all in between 0 and 55 basispoints. After this stable period, there is a specific moment where each bank suddenly has a big peak in their CDS prices. This can be explained by the impact of COVID-19, which had its formal introduction in February 2020. One can observe that the impact of COVID-19 on the CDS prices are different for each individual bank. Some got affected more than others, with Ally and MUFG Union as the outliers. They reach a maximum CDS price of 251.46 basispoints and 64.19 basispoints respectively. Then, there is a period where the CDS prices are dropping down until a new stable level again. This level seems to be higher than the one from the stable period of before. Table 1 gives a summary of the sample data statistics. The sample consists of nine banks, and is ordered by asset value of March 31, 2020. The asset values

are obtained from the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation, which is an official U.S. governmental institution. The asset values are given in billions of US \$. The CDS prices are given in basispoints.

No.	Institution	Total Asset	CDS (min)	CDS (max)	CDS (mean)
1	JP Morgan Chase	3,139	13.67	124.23	25.45
2	Bank of America	2,619	13.57	151.68	27.20
3	Citigroup	2,219	14.20	156.29	28.80
4	Wells Fargo	1,981	8.54	121.56	19.85
5	Goldman Sachs	1,089	15.94	136.56	32.04
6	Morgan Stanley	947	15.93	154.29	30.21
7	Capital One	396	9.06	46.07	17.25
8	Ally	182	11.27	251.46	53.23
9	MUFG Union	165	8.29	64.19	16.49

Table 1: Summary Sample Data Statistics

4 Model Implementation

Throughout this section, the CDS premium data of JP Morgan Chase is used to show the implementation of the model. Of course, the model implementation is exactly the same for the other banks, or financial institutions in general. First, the data will be prepared such that it works with the model and is in line with the research question. That means, the CDS premium data from the period far before the introduction of COVID-19 will be deleted. Furthermore, the CDS dates will be converted to years, with the earliest moment in time is at date $t=0$. Also the CDS premiums are converted from basispoints to actual values.

4.1 Implied risk-neutral default probability calculation

With the prepared data, the 1 year risk neutral probabilities of default will be calculated. To make sure the right probabilities are derived, the values are plotted. If correct, the pattern should look like the pattern of the CDS premiums. The corresponding R code can be found in line 95-112 of appendix B: R code. The 1 year risk neutral probabilities of default values correspond to the left hand side (LHS) of formula (7-14). Hence, the LHS is known for each moment in time t .

4.2 Log leverage ratio data estimation

The parameters will be set according to Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001) to calculate the first estimated log leverage ratio for each moment in time t according to formula (7-14). The implementation of formula (7-14) is difficult, since we are dealing with a highly complex function which involves summations of functions. Likewise, it is impossible to rewrite the formula as a function of the log leverage ratio l_t by hand. Therefore, numerical methods are used to obtain the correct estimated log leverage ratios. To be specific, we use a trial and error iteration process that changes the log leverage ratio l_t slightly until the right hand side (RHS) of formula (7-14) is approximately equal to the LHS of formula (7-14) for each moment in time t . The trial and error algorithm starts with a log leverage ratio of $l_t = 1$, and decreases this value until the LHS - RHS of formula (7-14) just turns positive. Or in other words, until the LHS and RHS of formula (7-14) are the same. The value of l_t decreases with 0.01 at each iteration. One could higher the accuracy by making these steps smaller. However, this will lower the algorithm's speed. Since the process is already computationally intense, this paper sticks to a 0.01 precision. The obtained log leverage data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$ will now be considered the initial estimated log leverage ratio data corresponding to the parameters of Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein (2001). The corresponding R code can be found in line 115-165 of appendix B: R code.

4.3 Parameter estimation

The maximum likelihood estimation method will be used to obtain better estimated parameters $\hat{\Theta}_j = (\hat{\mu}_j, \hat{\sigma}_j, \hat{\lambda}_j, \hat{\nu}_j)$ corresponding to the initial estimated log leverage ratio data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$. Since again, we are dealing with a highly complex log likelihood function, numerical methods are used to obtain those values. Hence, we start with some random initial parameter values and implement the log likelihood function from formula (16-19). Then the `optim()` function is used to solve the four dimensional maximization problem numerically. The `optim()` function uses a method called "Function minimization by conjugate gradients" developed by Fletcher and Reeves (1964), since this method ensures that the algorithm does converge, even for highly complex functions. The corresponding R code can be found in line 167-298 of appendix B: R code.

As a result, the new estimated parameters $\hat{\Theta}_j = (\hat{\mu}_j, \hat{\sigma}_j, \hat{\lambda}_j, \hat{\nu}_j)$ are obtained. With these new estimated parameters, the new estimated log leverage ratio data $(\hat{l}_{j,1}, \dots, \hat{l}_{j,m})$ will be constructed, again according to formula (7-14). The MLE method will be used again on this new estimated log leverage ratio data. This process will be repeated until the estimated parameters converge. The log leverage ratio data corresponding to these converged parameters, will then be the final estimated log leverage ratio data. The forloop in line 190 of appendix B: R code shows the repetition of the process.

4.4 Algorithm performance

To make sure the algorithm works properly, the whole process is done for different initial parameter values. That is, for $\Theta_j = (0.001, 0.200, 0.180, 1.106)$ and for $\Theta_j = (0.500, 0.500, 0.500, 0.750)$ The results are shown in Figure 2. One can see that with different initial parameters, we obtain the same converging ones, and as a result the same log leverage ratio data. Thus, the algorithm does converge in this specific setting, and so the model seems to work properly.

Figure 2: The MLE parameter convergence with different initial values

5 Results

Table 2 shows the converged MLE parameters for each individual bank according to the model. The table is ordered by asset value, just as the portfolio in table 1.

	μ	ν	σ	λ
JP Morgan Chase	0.7808799	0.9823933	1.160183	0.03776255
Bank of America	0.7750167	0.9805344	1.156173	0.03768152
Citigroup	0.7761028	0.9807317	1.156112	0.03878182
Wells Fargo	0.7784520	0.9819170	1.160342	0.03765461
Goldman Sachs	0.6495757	0.9656643	1.220068	-0.03846192
Morgan Stanley	0.6673087	0.9708744	1.227991	-0.03468033
Capital One	0.7711518	0.9824621	1.169182	0.03087708
Ally	0.8040146	0.9831568	1.140560	0.05444414
MUFG Union	0.7768024	0.9836386	1.167219	0.03071904

Table 2: Converged MLE parameters for each individual bank

One can see that the converged MLE parameter values from table 2 are all quite similar. This can be explained by the fact that the banks are all part of the U.S. financial sector. Nevertheless, there can still be seen a variety in values, especially for the parameters μ and σ . The values for ν and λ are for each bank quite similar, except for Goldman Sachs and Morgan Stanley. Those two banks have a negative value for λ and a slightly lower value for ν . To give an interpretation of the parameter values, recall that the asset dynamics, default threshold dynamics and the log leverage ratio dynamics from section are defined by:

$$d\ln(V_{j,t}) = (\mu_j - 0.5\sigma_j^2)dt + \sigma_j dW_{j,t}, \quad (20)$$

where μ_j denotes the expected drift and σ_j the volatility,

$$d\ln(K_{j,t}) = \lambda_j(\ln(V_{j,t}) - \nu_j - \ln(K_{j,t}))dt, \quad (21)$$

where λ_j denotes the institution's speed of adjustment to its log leverage ratio target and ν_j denotes the institution's log leverage ratio target,

$$d\ln(l_{j,t}) = \lambda_j(\bar{l} - l_{j,t})dt - \sigma_j dW_{j,t}, \quad (22)$$

where $\bar{l} = \frac{-\mu_j + 0.5\sigma_j^2}{\lambda_j} - \nu_j$.

Since the parameter values for μ are all positive, the expected drift for the asset value is upward sloping for each bank. Even though COVID-19 has raised all the CDS premiums dramatically, the asset values went up on average throughout the whole sample period according to the model.

The parameter values for ν are almost all the same and positive. This implies

that each bank is aiming for the same log leverage ratio target. This looks acceptable, since again, all the banks are part of the U.S. financial sector. It seems reasonable that firms from the same sector aim for the same financial stability. Note again, that the positive target value v corresponds to the aim towards a negative log leverage ratio. So the positive target values v seem to make sense. The parameter values for σ are all quite high, which means there is much volatility in the asset value over the whole sample period according to our model. These values would probably be way lower if the impact of COVID-19 would not have been taken into account.

The parameter values for λ are all similar and quite low. It shows the banks' speed of adjustment to its log leverage ratio target is low. In other words, the speed of adjustment of the log default threshold to the target level given by $(\ln(V_{j,t}) - v_j)$. It should be mentioned that the results for Goldman Sachs and Morgan Stanley are surprisingly negative. This implies that their speed of adjustment of the log default threshold is negative, which is odd. It means that they will never be able to reach their target level. This result questions the other obtained parameter values, as well as the whole model itself.

Figure 3 shows the corresponding log leverage ratios over time corresponding to these MLE parameters for each individual bank. On the right of each log leverage ratio plot, the distribution of the log leverage ratios is shown.

Figure 3: Log leverage ratios over time

Recall that the log leverage ratios are defined by $l_{j,t} = \ln(K_{j,t}/V_{j,t})$. So the closer the log leverage ratio values towards 0, the worse. For each individual bank holds that their log leverage ratio is in between -4.5 and -3.0. This implies that, throughout the whole sample period, the banks have been financially stable. MUFG Union has even gotten more financially stable after the introduction of COVID-19. Although for all the other banks hold that they are slightly less financially stable than before the impact of COVID-19, the effect seems to die out over time.

5.1 Intermediate Discussion

Since the negative values for λ from Morgan Stanley and Goldman Sachs question the reliability of the model, this needs to be investigated further. One of the reasons that a negative λ may occur, is that the model does not work well in crisis periods. To test whether this hypothesis is true, the model is applied to the CDS premiums of Morgan Stanley before the crisis period; from 2017-02-03 to 2018-12-14. Note that the sample size is still the same in this case. Figure 4 shows the log leverage ratios over time corresponding to this stable period.

Figure 4: Log Leverage Ratio over time Morgan Stanley stable period

The corresponding converged MLE parameters are given by: $\hat{\Theta}_j = (\hat{\mu}_j, \hat{\sigma}_j, \hat{\lambda}_j, \hat{\nu}_j) = (0.7479439, 1.173965, 0.02100972, 0.9790847)$. Observe that the value for λ is now positive. It indeed seems to be true that the model does not work well in periods of crisis. It could be interesting for further research to investigate this more.

6 Conclusion

The research question that has been investigated in this paper is: "What do Credit Default Swap premiums reveal about the financial stability of financial institutions in the U.S. during COVID-19?". To answer this research question, the following steps have been taken.

First, a literature review has been done in the introduction. The most relevant papers include (Merton, 1974), (Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein, 2001) and (Suh et al., 2013). Based on the existing literature the theoretical framework around Credit Default Swaps and financial stability has been constructed. The constructed theoretical framework can be summarized as follows: From CDS premiums, the risk-neutral probability of default can be obtained. With the risk-neutral probabilities of default the log leverage ratios can be calculated for each moment in time t , given assumed parameter values. The Maximum Likelihood Estimation Method can be used to give a better estimate of the initially assumed parameter values. With these better estimates, the log leverage ratios can be calculated again. This process can be repeated until the parameter values converge. This results in more accurate values for the log leverage ratios. By definition, the finally obtained log leverage ratios are an indicator of a firm's financial stability.

Then, an algorithm in R was developed to show how the implementation of the method works and to measure the financial stability of nine major banks in the U.S. during COVID-19 according to the method. To deal with highly complex functions, the algorithm works according to a trial and error process. Within each iteration, it deals with 4 dimensional optimization problems which makes the algorithm quite slow. The algorithm was tested with different initial parameter values to ensure it converges.

Finally, the model results of the nine major banks in the U.S. during COVID-19 were analyzed. The log leverage ratios from each individual bank turned out to have a value between -4.5 and -3.0, which can be seen as relatively financially stable. Besides that, the log leverage ratios for each individual bank became almost the same as before the introduction of COVID-19. This is in contradiction with our hypotheses that the banks became less financially stable after the introduction of COVID-19. Although the log leverage ratios seem to make sense, some parameter values obtained do not. This questions the reliability of the model. The result from the test in the intermediate discussion gives rise to the idea that the model does not work well in periods of crisis.

7 Further Research

For further research, it would be interesting to investigate further whether the model developed in this paper works well in periods of crisis. It might even be true, that the method works neither in periods of crisis nor in periods without crisis. Therefore, this is definitely the most important suggestion for further research. One could set up this experiment as done in section 5.1 but than on a greater scale. So one could apply the model on a large portfolio of financial institutions in a period of crisis and non-crisis and see how the estimated parameters differ. Another suggestion for further research is to try to increase the speed of the algorithm developed in this paper. One could gain the biggest advantage in the algorithm's speed by finding a solution that is not based on trial and error processes. This could make it easier for researchers working on the application of the model in the future. Once one is more certain about the reliability of the model, it can be applied to different situations.

8 References

References

- Akansu, Ali N and Mustafa U Torun (2015). *A primer for financial engineering: financial signal processing and electronic trading*. Academic Press.
- Black, Fischer and John C Cox (1976). Valuing corporate securities: Some effects of bond indenture provisions. *The Journal of Finance* 31(2), 351–367.
- Black, Fischer and Myron Scholes (1973). The pricing of options and corporate liabilities. *Journal of political economy* 81(3), 637–654.
- Collin-Dufresne, Pierre and Robert S Goldstein (2001). Do credit spreads reflect stationary leverage ratios? *The journal of finance* 56(5), 1929–1957.
- Cont, Rama et al. (2010). Credit default swaps and financial stability. *Financial Stability Review* 14(35), 35–43.
- Cont, Rama and Andreea Minca (2016). Credit default swaps and systemic risk. *Annals of Operations Research* 247(2), 523–547.
- Duffie, Darrell (1999). Credit swap valuation. *Financial Analysts Journal* 55(1), 73–87.
- Fama, Eugene F and Kenneth R French (2000). Forecasting profitability and earnings. *The Journal of Business* 73(2), 161–175.
- Fisher, Ronald Aylmer (1925). Theory of statistical estimation. In *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, Volume 22, pp. 700–725. Cambridge University Press.
- Fletcher, Reeves and Colin M Reeves (1964). Function minimization by conjugate gradients. *The computer journal* 7(2), 149–154.
- Huang, Xin, Hao Zhou, and Haibin Zhu (2009). A framework for assessing the systemic risk of major financial institutions. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 33(11), 2036–2049.
- Hull, John C and Alan D White (2000). Valuing credit default swaps i: No counterparty default risk. *The Journal of Derivatives* 8(1), 29–40.
- Lehar, Alfred (2005). Measuring systemic risk: A risk management approach. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 29(10), 2577–2603.
- Longstaff, Francis A and Eduardo S Schwartz (1995). A simple approach to valuing risky fixed and floating rate debt. *The Journal of Finance* 50(3), 789–819.

- Markose, Sheri, Simone Giansante, and Ali Rais Shaghghi (2012). 'too interconnected to fail' financial network of us cds market: Topological fragility and systemic risk. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization* 83(3), 627–646.
- Merton, Robert C (1974). On the pricing of corporate debt: The risk structure of interest rates. *The Journal of finance* 29(2), 449–470.
- Nijskens, Rob and Wolf Wagner (2011). Credit risk transfer activities and systemic risk: How banks became less risky individually but posed greater risks to the financial system at the same time. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 35(6), 1391–1398.
- Puliga, Michelangelo, Guido Caldarelli, and Stefano Battiston (2014). Credit default swaps networks and systemic risk. *Scientific reports* 4(1), 1–8.
- Senarath, Shanuka and Richard Copp (2015). Credit default swaps and the global financial crisis: reframing credit default swaps as quasi-insurance. *Global Economy and Finance Journal* 8(1), 135–149.
- Stulz, René M (2010). Credit default swaps and the credit crisis. *Journal of Economic Perspectives* 24(1), 73–92.
- Suh, Sangwon, Inwon Jang, and Misun Ahn (2013). A simple method for measuring systemic risk using credit default swap market data. *Journal of Economic Development* 38(4), 75.
- Terzi, Nuray and Korkmaz Ulucay (2011). The role of credit default swaps on financial market stability. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 24, 983–990.

9 Appendix A: Parameter overview

$V_{j,t}$: Value of the j 'th financial institution's asset at time t

$dW_{j,t} := d\epsilon\sqrt{t}$, where ϵ from $N(0,1)$ (Standard Wiener process)

μ_j : Expected drift j 'th financial institution's asset

σ_j : Volatility j 'th financial institution's asset

$K_{j,t}$: Default threshold j 'th financial institution's at time t (changes over time)

$l_{j,t}$: Log leverage ratio of j 'th financial institution at time t ($= \ln(K_{j,t}) - \ln(V_{j,t})$).

Default occurs when $l_{j,t}$ positive.

λ_j : Speed of adjustment to the log leverage ratio target of j 'th financial institution.

v_j : Log leverage ratio target j 'th financial institution

$$\bar{l} := \frac{-\mu_j + 0.5\sigma_j^2}{\lambda_j} - v_j$$

$Q(l_t, T)$: Default occurs before time T , given log leverage ratio at time t is l_t .

$$\Delta := \frac{T-t}{n}$$

T, t : The time in years

$\psi_{j,\tau}$: Annualized unconditional risk-neutral default density of the j 'th financial institution.

$\psi_{j,\tau}$: One-year risk-neutral default probability assuming density doesn't change between t and $t+T$

$s_{j,t}$: CDS premium j 'th financial institution at time t

10 Appendix B: R code

```
1 ### packages / Data ####
2 library(lubridate)
3 library(readr)
4 library(MASS)
5 library(patchwork)
6 library(ggplot2)
7 library(ggExtra)
8 library(readxl)
9 library(hrbrthemes)
10
11 ### Data preparation ####
12 JP_Morgan_Chase <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/JP Morgan Chase CSV (
  Excel).xlsx")
13 Bank_Of_America <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Bank Of America CDS (
  Excel).xlsx")
14 Wells_Fargo <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Wells Fargo CDS (Excel).
  xlsx")
15 Morgan_Stanley <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Morgan Stanley.xlsx")
16 Capital_One <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Capital One .xlsx")
17 Citigroup <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Citigroup.xlsx")
18 Goldman_Sachs <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Goldman Sachs.xlsx")
19 Ally <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/Ally.xlsx")
20 MUFJ <- read_excel("~/Desktop/Thesis/MUFJ.xlsx")
21
22 summary(Data9)
23
24 Data <- JP_Morgan_Chase
25 Data <- na.omit(Data)
26 names(Data) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
27 Data <- as.data.frame(Data)
28 summary(Data2)
29
30 Data2 <- Bank_Of_America
31 Data2 <- na.omit(Data2)
32 names(Data2) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
33 Data2 <- as.data.frame(Data2)
34
35
36 Data3 <- Wells_Fargo
37 Data3 <- na.omit(Data3)
38 names(Data3) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
39 Data3 <- as.data.frame(Data3)
40
41 Data4 <- Morgan_Stanley
42 Data4 <- na.omit(Data4)
43 names(Data4) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
44 Data4 <- as.data.frame(Data4)
45
46 Data5 <- Capital_One
47 Data5 <- na.omit(Data5)
48 names(Data5) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
49 Data5 <- as.data.frame(Data5)
50
51 Data6 <- Citigroup
52 Data6 <- na.omit(Data6)
```

```

53 names(Data6) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
54 Data6 <- as.data.frame(Data6)
55
56 Data7 <- Goldman_Sachs
57 Data7 <- na.omit(Data7)
58 names(Data7) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
59 Data7 <- as.data.frame(Data7)
60
61 Data8 <- Ally
62 Data8 <- na.omit(Data8)
63 names(Data8) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
64 Data8 <- as.data.frame(Data8)
65
66 Data9 <- MUFG
67 Data9 <- na.omit(Data9)
68 names(Data9) <- c("Date", "CDS") #Change names of data
69 Data9 <- as.data.frame(Data9)
70
71 ### Data Visualization ###
72 colors <- c("JP Morgan Chase" = "Blue", "Bank Of America" = "Red", "
       Wells Fargo" = "Green",
73           "Morgan Stanley" = "aquamarine3", "Capital One" = "
       darkgoldenrod1", "Citigroup" = "darkgreen",
74           "Goldman Sachs" = "darkorchid", "Ally" = "deeppink", "MUFG
       Union" = "rosybrown")
75 ggplot() + geom_line(Data[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS,
       color= "JP Morgan Chase")) +
76   geom_line(Data2[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Bank Of America")) +
77   geom_line(Data3[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Wells Fargo")) +
78   geom_line(Data4[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Morgan Stanley")) +
79   geom_line(Data5[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Capital One")) +
80   geom_line(Data6[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Citigroup")) +
81   geom_line(Data7[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Goldman Sachs")) +
82   geom_line(Data8[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       Ally")) +
83   geom_line(Data9[1:486,], mapping = aes(x = Date, y = CDS, color = "
       MUFG Union")) +
84   ggtitle("CDS prices per bank over time") +
85   theme_ipsum() +
86   ylab("CDS (basispoints)") +
87   labs(color = "Bank") +
88   scale_color_manual(values = colors)
89
90 ### Setting some parameters and defining e as the e value ###
91 r = 0.001
92 LGD = 1
93 e <- exp(1)
94
95 ###Transformation of CDS data from EIKON / PD data from EIKON ###
96 JPMICDS <- Data[1:486,] #(intro covid december 2019) CDS in
       basispoints (*0.0001), I think yearly

```

```

97 JPM1CDS <- JPM1CDS[(order(JPM1CDS$Date)), ]
98 JPM1CDS$Date <- decimal_date(as.Date(JPM1CDS$Date, format = "%d-%m-%Y")
   ) #transform dates to decimal date (half year = 0.5 etc.)
99 JPM1CDS$Date <- JPM1CDS$Date-JPM1CDS[1,1] #transform date s.t. first
   date is t=0
100
101 JPM1CDS. <-JPM1CDS[1:486,2]*0.0001 # CDS in values instead of
   basispoints
102
103 ### Calculation 1 year probability of default for each CDS value at
   time t according to formula (6) ####
104 integrand1 <- function(t) {e^{-r*t}}
105 integrand2 <- function(t) {t*e^{-r*t}}
106 pd <- c()
107 for (i in 1:nrow(JPM1CDS) ){
108   pd[i] <- ( (JPM1CDS.[i]) * integrate(integrand1, lower = JPM1CDS[i
   ,1], upper = JPM1CDS[i,1] + 1 )$value ) / ( 1 * integrate(
   integrand1, lower = JPM1CDS[i,1], upper = JPM1CDS[i,1] + 1)$value +
   (JPM1CDS.[i]) * integrate(integrand2, lower = JPM1CDS[i,1], upper
   = JPM1CDS[i,1] + 1)$value )
109 }
110
111 ### Plot of default probabilities ####
112 plot(pd)
113
114
115 ### Q(lt, 1) calculation formula 7-14. LHS of equality sign is known,
   RHS depends on parameter l (loglevratio) ####
116 #parameters are set the same as Collin-Dufresne and Goldstein
117 sigma <- 0.2
118 lambda <- 0.18
119 lbar <- -1
120 nu <- (-r + 0.5*sigma^2)/lambda - lbar
121 n <- 10
122 delta <- (2 - 1)/n
123
124 #defining functions (11), (13), (14)
125 S <- function(t) {sqrt((sigma^2)/(2*lambda)*(1-e^{-2*lambda*t}))}
126 L <- function(t) {lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*t})}
127 b <- function(i) {L(i*delta)/S(i*delta)}
128
129
130 ll <- c() #empty vector that will store the numerically obtained log
   leverage ratios at each time t.
131 for (tt in 1:nrow(JPM1CDS)) {
132   delta <- (2 - 1)/n
133
134   QQ <- c() #empty vector that will store for each different try of l
   the 1 year default probability according to model
135   for (k in 300:1000) {
136
137     l <- 1 - 0.01*k #log leverage ratio that slightly changes for each
   iteration to eventually obtain the right 1 year prob of default and
   so the right log leverage ratio at time t
138     q <- c()
139     Q <- c()
140

```

```

141 i=1
142 q[1] <- {pnorm(1*e^{-lambda*i*delta} + lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*i*delta}))
/S(i*delta))/pnorm(b(1/2))} #defining function (8), calculates q1
143
144
145 for (i in 2:n){ #defining function (9) from paper, calculates q2
... ,qn
146 Q <- c()
147 for (j in 1:i-1){
148 Q[j] <- q[j]*b(i-j+1/2)
149 }
150 q[i] <- { (1/pnorm(b(1/2))) * (pnorm(1*e^{-lambda*i*delta} + lbar
*(1-e^{-lambda*i*delta}))/S(i*delta)) - sum(Q))}
151 }
152
153 QQ[k] <- sum(q) #defining function (7) from paper, calculates Q(lt,
1)
154
155 print(pd[tt]-QQ[k]) #shows difference between calculated pd and
actual pd for each different l
156
157 if (pd[tt] - QQ[k] > 0) {break()} #if difference = 0, the right l
has been found. Since never exactly equal to 0, when difference > 0
algorithm stops iteration
158
159 }
160
161 #plot(pd[tt] - QQ)
162 QQ
163 ll[tt] <- l #stores for each moment in time the obtained log leverage
ratio
164
165 }
166
167 ### Loglikelihood estimation ####
168 mu <- 1 #inititial guess
169 nu <- 1 #inititial guess
170 sigma <- 1 #inititial guess
171 lambda <- 0.1 #inititial guess
172 muu <- c()
173 nuu <- c()
174 sigmaa <- c()
175 lambdaa <- c()
176 OPTIMM <- c()
177 for (h in 1:20) {
178 muu[h] <- mu
179 nuu[h] <- nu
180 sigmaa[h] <- sigma
181 lambdaa[h] <- lambda
182
183
184 loglikelihood <- function(param) {
185
186 mu <- param[1]
187 nu <- param[2]
188 sigma <- param[3]
189 lambda <- param[4]

```

```

190 lbar <- (-mu + 0.5*sigma^2)/lambda - nu
191
192 #first part
193 L1 <- (-(length(l1)-1)/2)*log(2*pi) - ((length(l1)-1)/2)*log((sigma^2
194 /2*lambda)*e^{-lambda*delta}*(e^{2*lambda*delta}-1) )
195 #second part
196 L22 <- c()
197
198 for (i in 2:length(l1)){
199   L22[1] <- 0
200   L22[i] <- (( l1[i]-l1[i-1]*e^{-lambda*delta}-lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*
201   delta})))^2 / ( (sigma^2/2*lambda)*e^{-lambda*delta}*(e^{2*lambda*
202   delta}-1) )
203   L2 <- -0.5*sum(L22)
204 }
205
206 #third part
207 L33 <- c()
208 L33[1] <- 0
209 dQQ <- c()
210 dQQ[1] <- 0
211 for (m in 2:length(l1)){
212
213   dq <- c()
214   dQ <- c()
215   i=1
216   dq[1] <- {dnorm(l1[m]*e^{-lambda*i*delta} + lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*i*
217   delta}))/S(i*delta))/pnorm(b(1/2)) * ((e^{-lambda*delta}))/S(delta*i
218   ))} #defining function (18) from paper, calculates dq1 (i=1)
219
220   for (i in 2:n){ #defining function (19), calculates dq2,...,dqn
221     dQ <- c()
222     for (j in 1:i-1){
223       dq[j] <- dq[j]*b(i-j+1/2)
224     }
225     dq[i] <- { (1/pnorm(b(1/2))) * (dnorm(l1[m]*e^{-lambda*i*delta}
226     + lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*i*delta}))/S(i*delta))*((e^{-lambda*delta}))/S
227     (delta*i)) - sum(dQ)}
228   }
229
230   dQQ[m] <- sum(dq) #defining function (17) from paper, calculates
231   dQ(lt, 1)
232
233   L33[m] <- dQQ[m]
234   L3 <- -log(sum(L33))
235 }
236
237 loglik <- L1+L2+L3
238 return(loglik)

```

```

239 OPTIM <- optim(c(mu,nu,sigma,lambda), loglikelihood, control = list(
      fnscale = -1), method = "CG") #MLE method; 4 dimensional
      optimization
240
241 mu <- OPTIM$par[1]
242 nu <- OPTIM$par[2]
243 sigma <- OPTIM$par[3]
244 lambda <- OPTIM$par[4]
245
246
247 ### Q(lt, 1) calculation formula 7-14. LHS of equality sign is known,
      RHS depends on parameter l (loglevratio) #### #parameters are set
      as obtained form MLE
248 lbar <- (-mu + 0.5*sigma^2)/lambda - nu
249 n <- 10
250 delta <- (2 - 1)/n
251
252 #defining functions (11), (13), (14)
253 S <- function(t) {sqrt((sigma^2)/(2*lambda)*(1-e^{-2*lambda*t}))}
254 L <- function(t) {lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*t})}
255 b <- function(i) {L(i*delta)/S(i*delta)}
256
257
258 ll <- c() #empty vector that will store the numerically obtained log
      leverage ratios at eacht time t.
259 for (tt in 1:nrow(JPM1CDS)) {
260   delta <- (2 - 1)/n
261
262   QQ <- c() #empty vector that will store for each different try of l
      the 1 year default probability according to model
263   for (k in 300:1000) {
264
265     l <- 1 - 0.01*k #log leverage ratio that slightly changes for
      each iteration to eventually obtain the right 1 year prob of
      default and so the right log leverage ratio at time t
266     q <- c()
267     Q <- c()
268
269     i=1
270     q[1] <- {pnorm(1*e^{-lambda*i*delta} + lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*i*delta}
      ))/S(i*delta))/pnorm(b(1/2))} #defining function (8), calculates q1
271
272
273     for (i in 2:n){ #defining function (8), calculates q2,...,qn
274       Q <- c()
275       for (j in 1:i-1){
276         Q[j] <- q[j]*b(i-j+1/2)
277       }
278       q[i] <- { (1/pnorm(b(1/2))) * (pnorm(1*e^{-lambda*i*delta} +
      lbar*(1-e^{-lambda*i*delta}))/S(i*delta)) - sum(Q)}
279     }
280
281     QQ[k] <- sum(q) #defining function (7) from paper, calculates Q(
      lt, 1)
282
283     #print(pd[tt]-QQ[k]) #shows difference between calculated pd and
      actual pd for each different l

```

```

284   if (pd[tt] - QQ[k] > 0) {break()} #if difference = 0, the right l
      has been found. Since never exactly equal to 0, when difference >
      0 algorithm stops iteration
285
286   }
287   #print(k)
288   #plot(pd[tt] - QQ)
289   #QQ
290   ll[tt] <- l #stores for each moment in time the obtained log
      leverage ratio
291
292   }
293   OPTIMM[h] <- OPTIM$convergence
294   print(h)
295   print(OPTIMM[h])
296   plot (ll)
297
298 }
299 par(mfrow=c(2,2))
300 plot(muu, ylab = "Mu", xlab = "iteration", col = "red")
301 plot(nuu, ylab = "Nu", xlab = "iteration", col = "green")
302 plot(sigmaa, ylab = "Sigma", xlab = "iteration", col = "purple")
303 plot(lambdaa, ylab = "Lambda", xlab = "iteration", col = "blue")
304
305 muu
306 nuu
307 sigmaa
308 lambdaa
309
310 ### Visualizations ###
311 JPM1CDS <- Data[1:486,]
312 JPM1CDS <- JPM1CDS[ (order(JPM1CDS$Date)), ]
313 Dates <- as.Date(JPM1CDS$Date)
314
315 lldata <- cbind.data.frame(Dates, ll)
316
317 p <- ggplot(lldata, mapping = aes(x = Dates, y = ll)) + geom_point(
      color = "aquamarine3", alpha = 0, size = 0.3) + geom_line(color = "
      rosybrown") +
318   ggtitle("Log Leverage Ratio over time MIFG Union") +
319   scale_x_date(breaks = as.Date(c("2019-01-01", "2019-04-01", "
      2019-07-01", "2019-10-01", "2020-01-01",
320     "2020-04-01", "2020-07-01", "
      2020-10-01", "2020-01-01")), date_labels = "%Y (%b)") +
321   scale_y_continuous(limits = c(-4.5, -3), expand = c(0, 0)) +
322   theme_ipsum() +
323   ylab("Log Leverage Ratio") +
324   xlab("Date")
325
326 # Show only marginal plot for x axis
327 p3 <- ggMarginal(p, margins = 'y', color="rosybrown", type = "density")
328 p3

```